

Original Research

Capital Structure Mediation: Profitability and Dividend Policy Effects on Firm Value in IDX-Listed Service Firms, 2022–2024

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the influence of profitability and dividend policy on firm value, with capital structure acting as a mediating factor, specifically within service sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange during the 2022–2024 period. This study utilizes panel data regression techniques and SEM PLS bootstrapping mediation tests for analysis. The findings indicate that profitability has a positive and significant impact on firm value, underscoring its essential role as an indicator of corporate reliability and performance. Conversely, dividend policy does not significantly affect firm value, suggesting that dividends have a limited role in determining the value within Indonesia's service sector. Furthermore, profitability negatively and significantly influences capital structure, as companies with higher profits tend to reduce their reliance on debt for operational financing. Capital structure neither directly affects nor mediates the relationship between dividend policy and firm value. However, it negatively mediates profitability and firm value. These results highlight the importance of enhancing profitability and effectively managing capital structure, as well as the necessity of tailoring management strategies to industry-specific characteristics. The study also recommends broadening the range of variables considered and testing in other sectors to enrich the understanding of firm value formation in Indonesia.

Keywords: Capital Structure, Dividend Policy, Firm Value, Profitability.

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Introduction

Firm value constitutes a comprehensive evaluation of a company's financial health and prospective growth as perceived by investors, creditors, and other stakeholders (Dimitropoulos, 2022; Huynh et al., 2022). It plays a crucial role in shaping corporate strategies as it directly influences decisions regarding resource allocation, capital acquisition, and shareholder returns (Tayachi et al., 2023). The primary determinants of firm value are profitability, dividend policies, and capital structure (Al-Omari et al., 2023). These financial components are essential for strategic financial management and the generation of long-term value (M, 2019; Nguyen et al., 2023; Sari, 2020; Sondakh, 2019). They constitute the fundamental elements necessary for strategic financial management and assurance of sustainable value creation.

Profitability is a key indicator of a company's capacity to generate earnings relative to its expenses and assets (Caceres, 2024; Zhang & Wang, 2022a). It plays a crucial role in determining sustainable growth, investor confidence and creditworthiness (Zhang & Wang, 2022b). High profitability enables reinvestment in research, development, and expansion, thereby enhancing market competitiveness (Valaskova et al., 2021). Dividend policy dictates the allocation of a company's earnings between reinvestment and distribution to shareholders (Lin et al., 2023; Sondakh, 2019). By establishing the proportion of profits to be distributed, companies communicate their financial strategies and long-term objectives to stakeholders (Driver et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2023). A consistent dividend policy bolsters investor confidence and influences market valuations (Arhinful et al., 2024). Capital structure, which consists of a mix of debt and equity financing, affects both the cost of capital and financial risk (Al Amosh et al., 2024; Arhinful et al., 2024). An effectively managed capital structure leverages the advantages of debt, such as tax benefits, while ensuring that adequate equity is available to address unforeseen circumstances and maintain flexibility (Al Amosh et al., 2024). Therefore, it entails the judicious utilization of debt to secure advantages, such as tax savings, while ensuring the retention of adequate equity to address unforeseen challenges and maintain adaptability.

In Indonesia's service industry, financial considerations are particularly significant because of the sector's reliance on intangible assets, workforce, and customer relationships (Dancaková et al., 2022; Oduro, 2024; Sondakh, 2019; Wahjudi, 2019). Unlike manufacturing firms, service enterprises derive their value from operational efficiency and client engagement (Arhinful et al., 2024; Pinto & Rastogi, 2019; Rastogi & Singh, 2025). Dividend policies often require a balance between reinvesting in innovation and maintaining investors' interests (Sondakh, 2019; Tayachi et al., 2023). Decisions regarding capital structure must consider the volatility and financial constraints characteristic of Indonesia's service sector (Arhinful et al., 2024). These factors affect what kind of capital structure is appropriate or sustainable for these companies.

In addition to financial metrics, service companies must consider the specific market conditions and cultural nuances of the regions in which they operate (Shi, 2023). Factors such as consumer preferences, purchasing behavior, and competitive dynamics significantly influence product and service development (Rusdian et al., 2024). Cultural aspects, including communication strategies and relationship-building techniques, are

essential for fostering trust (Gupta & Shukla, 2024). Furthermore, regulatory frameworks shape operational decisions by establishing compliance and industry standards (Rahman et al., 2024). Although extensive research exists on the determinants of firm value, it predominantly focuses on manufacturing or multinational corporations, often overlooking the unique characteristics of service sector businesses in emerging markets (Ali et al., 2022; Rajverma et al., 2019). Previous studies have typically considered profitability, dividend policies, and capital structure as isolated factors without examining their interrelated dynamics or the mechanisms through which they affect each other (Kanakriyah, 2020; M, 2019; Sari, 2020; Sondakh, 2019).

Furthermore, current models often depend on pooled cross-sectional data, overlooking both temporal and firm-specific differences (Castro & Ariño, 2016). They also fail to fully utilize panel data methods and do not adequately address issues such as outlier distortion, endogeneity, and sample selection bias, particularly in firms that pay dividends (Carlson & Joshi, 2024; Tinungki et al., 2022). The innovations of this study are highlighted as follows:

1. This study is dedicated solely to Indonesian service companies, a sector that is not extensively covered in empirical finance studies.
2. By employing panel data from 2022 to 2024 to observe firm-level changes over time, we discovered that.
3. Examining capital structure as an intermediary variable, linking profitability and dividend policy to firm value.
4. We address methodological shortcomings through comprehensive diagnostics, winsorization, and panel estimation methods, including random and fixed effects with the Hausman test.
5. This study offers contextual insights pertinent to Indonesia's regulatory, cultural, and economic environments.

This study targets service companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) because of their crucial role in driving national economic growth. These companies operate in sectors such as finance, telecommunications, and professional services. The period from 2022 to 2024 aligns with a phase of rapid change, characterized by digitalization, regulatory changes, and evolving investor behavior. This study empirically investigates how profitability and dividend policy affect firm value, with capital structure serving as a mediating factor (Sondakh, 2019; SUDIYATNO et al., 2020). By considering the unique traits of service firms, this study ensures its relevance to Indonesia's specific market conditions. Understanding the mediating function of capital structure offers deeper insights into how financial strategies impact the connections between earnings performance, dividend distribution, and firm valuation (Bataineh et al., 2022).

In addition, this study enhances the broader understanding of accounting and finance in emerging markets. By addressing the distinct challenges faced by service firms and investors in Indonesia, this study provides practical insights for enhancing financial decision-making and firm performance. These findings are also pertinent to policymakers

aiming to improve corporate governance frameworks, promote transparency and increase accountability (Sebrina et al., 2023; Shan et al., 2024).

Literature Review

Trade Off Theory

Several factors limit companies from incurring unlimited debt, primarily due to the increased likelihood of bankruptcy associated with higher debt levels (Chen et al., 2017). The trade-off theory posits that firms establish an optimal capital structure by balancing the benefits of the interest tax shield against the costs of financial distress, considering taxes, agency costs, and bankruptcy risk (Abdeljawad & Farhood, 2025). This framework guides managers in enhancing firm value through a strategic balance between debt and equity (Brahmayanti, 2024). Debt within the capital structure offers tax shield advantages, as interest payments reduce taxable income, thereby lowering tax liability and the cost of debt, while increasing profitability (Gregova et al., 2021). Additionally, regular interest payments serve as a mechanism for management discipline, promoting operational efficiency (Modigliani & Miller, 1958). However, excessive debt entails risks, including bankruptcy costs, agency costs arising from shareholder-creditor conflicts, and financial distress (Issa et al., 2024; Kamaluddin et al., 2019). High interest expenses can constrain cash flows and jeopardize business continuity if firms are unable to meet their financial obligations (Kamaluddin et al., 2019).

Signalling Theory

Signaling theory pertains to the actions undertaken by a company to convey information to investors regarding management's perspective on the company's potential (Smith & Pennathur, 2019). Signals constitute pieces of information that reflect management's efforts to fulfill the objectives of the owners (Al Amosh et al., 2024; Vijayakumaran & Vijayakumaran, 2019). This information can be communicated through a company's capital structure decisions, such as issuing new shares or acquiring funds through debt (Tayachi et al., 2023). A signal serves as a mechanism for management to indicate to investors that the shareholder expectations have been met (Tayachi et al., 2023). The relationship between signaling theory and firm value is evident in how companies transmit positive signals through favorable information to investors (Blagoeva et al., 2020; Brochet et al., 2021). The information disseminated by management can function as a signal for investors when making investment decisions (Eckbo & Kisser, 2021). In this study, profitability and capital structure, as announced by management, demonstrate confidence in the company's capacity for robust future growth, thereby enhancing investor trust (Hans et al., 2024; PAVOLOVÁ et al., 2021).

Agency Theory

In the domain of corporate financial policy, agency theory posits that profitability, dividend policy, and capital structure function as mechanisms for mitigating agency conflicts (Driver et al., 2020; Tayachi et al., 2023). Firms with substantial profitability often generate free cash flow, which managers may allocate to projects that lack value addition (Byoun et al., 2016; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). By distributing regular

dividends, companies can restrict the funds available for managerial discretion while simultaneously conveying positive signals to the market (Driver et al., 2020; Smith & Pennathur, 2019). This study employs agency theory as a framework to demonstrate that high profitability necessitates effective management to avoid agency conflicts (Berzins et al., 2018; Driver et al., 2020). Dividend policy serves as a mechanism to address free cash flow issues by enforcing managerial discipline and distributing cash to shareholders, thereby reducing agency costs and enhancing company valuation (Driver et al., 2020). Furthermore, financial leverage acts as both a mediating factor and an additional governance tool, particularly through the discipline associated with debt, which influences managerial behavior and ultimately enhances shareholder value (Tayachi et al., 2023).

Bird In The Hand Theory

This study is closely associated with the Bird-in-the-Hand theory, particularly concerning the management of dividend distribution and its effect on a company's valuation (Driver et al., 2020; Muriungi & Mwang, 2020). High profitability, as evidenced by substantial net income, is essential for sustaining a consistent cash dividend policy (Baker & Jabbouri, 2017). According to Gordon (1959), firms with strong financial performance can provide regular cash flows to investors through dividend payments. This theory posits that companies with greater profitability can distribute regular and larger dividends, thereby enhancing their attractiveness to investors (Pinto & Rastogi, 2019). Investors perceive profitability as an indicator of the reliability of future dividend payments, which mitigates uncertainty and increases their propensity to invest in the company's stock (Dewasiri et al., 2019; Gormsen & Lazarus, 2023).

Hypothesis Development

The Influence of Profitability on Firm Value

According to Signaling Theory, supported by empirical evidence from non-financial service companies listed on the IDX between 2022 and 2024, a company's ability to generate earnings serves as a significant indicator for investors (Agustia et al., 2020). Service firms that achieve high profitability demonstrate effective business strategies, efficient operations, and strong cost and revenue management capabilities (Alarussi & Gao, 2023; Sondakh, 2019). This reflects the quality of management and robustness of the business model (Nadukuru et al., 2024; Okeke et al., 2024). Furthermore, strong profitability is often regarded as a reliable predictor of future profits. Investors generally believe that companies that generate profits will continue to do so, leading to increased cash flows and enhanced company value (Dancaková et al., 2022; Kapoor & Goel, 2017; Markonah et al., 2020). In the service industry, where intangible assets such as reputation and service quality are crucial, profitability is a vital quantitative measure for assessing performance (Orhangazi, 2019; Serpeninova et al., 2022). By reporting high profitability, managers convey a signal that reduces information asymmetry, reassuring investors that the company is a worthwhile investment (Hasnat et al., 2024) (Atiningsih, 2017).

Studies conducted by (Aprianti et al., 2022; Fuhrotun, 2022; Kusumawati et al., 2020; Rachman, 2024; Ramadhani et al., 2024; Saputri & Giovanni, 2021; R. M. Sari & Candra,

2024; Wibowo & Yuliana, 2020; Wilson, 2020) found that profitability has a positive and significant effect on firm value. In contrast, (Samiun et al., 2022; Fauziah & Nurhayati, 2023; Mispiyanti & Wicaksono, 2020) found that profitability does not affect company valuation. In this study, profitability is measured using the Return on Assets (ROA) ratio, while the Price-to-Book Value (PBV) ratio is used to assess the firm's market value. Based on this discussion, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₁: Profitability positively impacts firm value.

The Influence of Dividend Decisions on Firm Value

In alignment with the Bird-in-the-Hand Theory and empirical observations of non-financial service companies listed on the IDX from 2022 to 2024, it is apparent that during the uncertain post-pandemic recovery phase, investors demonstrated increased caution (Amar et al., 2018; Arhinful et al., 2024; Bustani et al., 2021). Non-financial service companies that maintain or enhance their cash dividend policies assure returns and mitigate perceived risks for investors (Rastogi & Singh, 2025). Companies that consistently distribute dividends are more attractive to investors because they provide a reliable income source (Lin et al., 2023; Sondakh, 2019). When non-financial service companies sustain or increase dividend payments during economic recovery, it sends a positive signal to the market regarding their financial health and long-term viability (El-Deeb & Allam, 2024). Signaling Theory suggests that dividend policy can serve as an indicator of future profitability and the robustness of a company's cash flow (Smith & Pennathur, 2019) At its core, a company's dividend policy reflects its financial stability and potential for generating profits..

This implies that the company has not only recovered but also possesses a strong capacity to generate cash and is confident in its future growth (Stereńczak & Kubiak, 2022). Investors perceive regular dividend payments as a favorable indicator of financial stability and promising prospects, thereby enhancing investor confidence and demand for the company's stock (Driver et al., 2020). As noted by Brigham & Houston (2022), a stable dividend policy enhances investors' perceptions of investment security and positively influences a company's market valuation.

Selvy & Esra (2022); Seran et al. (2023); Simanjuntak & Hasibuan (2023); Yanti & Setiawati (2022), found that dividend policy significantly and positively affects firm value, while Anindya & Muzakir (2023; Efpriati & Sumarni (2024) found no significant effect. In this study, the dividend policy variable is represented by the DPR, and corporate value is proxied by the PBV. Based on the information provided, the following hypothesis is proposed:

H₂: Dividend decisions positively influence firm's value.

The Influence of Profitability on Capital Structure

Agency Theory, as articulated by Jensen & Meckling (1976), highlights conflicts of interest and information asymmetry between principals (shareholders) and agents (managers) (Tayachi et al., 2023). These conflicts create agency costs that influence

financial decisions, particularly capital structure. Agency theory presents two perspectives on profitability and capital structure (John et al., 2021). First, regarding debt-related agency costs, highly profitable companies with substantial internal cash flows prefer internal financing to avoid creditor disputes (Myers & Majluf, 1984). External borrowing can introduce agency costs like underinvestment risk (Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Kashefi & Eilnaz, 2017). Profitable firms often choose equity-heavy structures, as creditors' restrictive covenants may prompt managers to avoid debt (Gong et al., 2024).

Second, regarding equity agency costs, profitable companies with significant free cash flow might invest in unprofitable ventures (Hoffmann & Kleimeier, 2021). Jensen (1983) suggests debt as a disciplinary mechanism, as payment obligations limit managers' discretionary funds. The relationship between profitability and capital structure varies based on agency cost management (Carbó-Valverde et al., 2022). While (Pramana & Darmayanti, 2020; Savitri et al., 2021), found negative effects on capital structure, Wulandari & Januri (2020) identified does not have an relationships. This study uses ROA for profitability and DER for capital structure.

H₃: Profitability negatively influences capital structure.

The Influence of Dividend Policy on Capital Structure

Agency Theory, as articulated by Jensen (1983) in his seminal work on Free Cash Flow Agency Costs, offers a framework for comprehending the influence of high dividend policies on capital structure and managerial discipline, particularly within non-financial service companies listed on the IDX from 2022 to 2024. Companies in the service sector that are in the recovery phase and generating substantial profits often possess significant free cash flow (Arhinful et al., 2024; Guizani, 2018). The decision to implement high dividend payouts reduces the free cash flow available to managers, thereby limiting the potential for fund misuse (Jensen, 1983). Consequently, with diminished internal resources, managers are compelled to seek external financing for future investments (Bae et al., 2021). Debt financing emerges as a favorable option because it provides the necessary capital and involves creditor oversight through debt covenants, which mitigates managerial opportunism and reduces agency costs (Arhinful et al., 2024; Jensen & Meckling, 1976; Tran & Ashraf, 2018).

The strategic combination of high dividend payouts and debt financing enhances the disciplinary framework, incentivizing managers to pursue only those investments that are efficient and capable of generating sufficient cash flows to meet debt obligations and sustain dividend payments (Arhinful et al., 2024; Jensen, 1983). Mispriyanti & Wicaksono (2020; Tayachi et al. (2023); Zou & Bai (2022) indicate that dividend policy positively influences capital structure and firm value, whereas (Mahirun et al. (2023) find no significant effect. In this study, dividend policy is represented by the Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR), and capital structure is represented by the Debt-to-Equity Ratio (DER).

H₄: Dividend policy positively affects capital structure.

The Effect of Capital Structure on Firm Value

Capital Structure Theory, particularly the Trade-Off Theory, offers a theoretical framework for elucidating the relationship between capital structure and firm value (Husna & Satria, 2019). This theory posits that firms strive to achieve an optimal level of debt by balancing the tax benefits of interest (tax shields) against the costs associated with bankruptcy (Cevheroglu-Acar, 2018). When debt levels are maintained within reasonable limits, a firm's value increases due to tax savings and enhanced managerial discipline. Conversely, an excessive debt burden can diminish firm value due to bankruptcy costs, agency conflict, and risks associated with financial distress (Jensen & Meckling, 2000).

Debt becomes particularly hazardous when it surpasses a company's equity (Alam et al., 2024). Research conducted by Alghifari et al. (2022) and Kurniasih et al. (2022) demonstrated that capital structure exerts a positive and significant impact on firm valuation, whereas Ayem & Tamu Ina (2023) and Susanti et al. (2023) found no significant effect. In this analysis, the capital structure is represented by the DER, and firm value by the PBV.

H₅: A firm's capital structure configuration positively affects firm value.

The Intervening Role of Capital Structure in the Profitability–Firm Value Relationship

In the Agency Model framework, profitable companies, particularly in the service sector (2022-2024), tend to generate increased free cash flow (Guo et al., 2021). Jensen (1983) suggests substantial free cash flow may lead to wasteful managerial decisions. Companies may increase their debt levels as a disciplinary mechanism because interest payments and creditor oversight require careful resource allocation (Dagnino et al., 2019; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Optimal debt levels can reduce agency costs and enhance firm value through disciplined management (John et al., 2021). Investors favor companies with well-managed capital structures, making capital structure an intermediary between profitability and firm value (Nguyen et al., 2023). Mubyarto (2020) and Supeno (2022) showed that profitability positively influences firm value through capital structure, while Hamdani et al. (2022) and Mispriyanti & Wicaksono (2020) found no mediating effects. Profitability, capital structure, and firm value are measured using ROA, DER, and PBV, respectively.

H₆: The capital structure mediates the relationship between profitability and firm value.

The Intervening Role of Capital Structure in the Dividend Policy –Firm Value Relationship

In Agency Theory, when service-sector firms on the IDX (2022-2024) adopt high dividend policies, managers' free cash flow is reduced (Guizani, 2018). Jensen (1983) states this limits managerial opportunism. Companies may increase their debt to finance projects, with debt serving as a disciplinary mechanism through payment obligations and creditor oversight (Tayachi et al., 2023).

An optimal debt capital structure can enhance firm value by reducing agency costs and promoting efficiency (Antón & Lin, 2020). Investors favor companies that limit managerial discretion, making the capital structure a channel through which dividend policy influences valuation (Njoku & Lee, 2024).

Susanti et al. (2023) found that capital composition mediates the effect of dividend policy on market value, while Mispiyanti & Wicaksono (2020) found no mediation. DPR represents the dividend policy, DER the capital structure, and PBV the firm value.

H7: The capital structure mediates the relationship between dividend policy and firm value.

Methodology

Type of Research

This study uses a quantitative research methodology involving the systematic collection of quantifiable data through statistical and computational techniques. Quantitative research is widely used in the natural and physical sciences (Priadana et al., 2021).

This research is causal, aiming to identify the relationships between variables. It includes independent variables (profitability and dividend policy), a dependent variable (firm value), and an intervening variable (leverage). The study uses regression and path analysis, with path analysis examining the direct and indirect effects of profitability and dividend policy on firm value through capital structure.

Research Location and Period

This study examines non-financial service companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) from 2022 to 2024. The focus on non-financial sectors is due to their unique operational characteristics. The research population comprised 346 service companies.

Using purposive sampling, companies were selected based on the following criteria: continuous IDX listing during 2022-2024, non-financial service sector classification, complete audited financial statements in Rupiah, and consistent cash dividend distribution. Based on these criteria, 39 companies qualified as research subjects.

The companies chosen as samples based on the aforementioned criteria are as follows.

Table 1. Sample Selection Criteria

Keterangan	Jumlah
Service companies listed on the IDX (2022–2024)	346
Financial sector companies	(105)
Companies delisted (2022–2024)	(10)
Companies not publishing financial statements consecutively (2022–2024)	(2)

Keterangan	Jumlah
Companies not distributing dividends consecutively (2022–2024)	(190)
Companies reporting in currencies other than Rupiah	(0)
Final Sample	39

Data Collection Tools and Techniques

Microsoft Excel recorded the data, while Eviews 12 and SEM PLS 4 were used to analyze it. Data collection involved downloading information from the audited annual financial statements of service companies on the Indonesia Stock Exchange (IDX) for 2022–2024. Sources included the IDX website (www.idx.co.id) and the company websites. The collected documents were the statement of financial position, income statement, cash flow statement, and notes to financial statements, forming the basis for research variables such as profitability, dividend policy, capital structure, company size, economic uncertainty, and firm value. The following indicators were used:

Table 2. Variable Measurement

Variable	Description	Scale Measurement	Scale
Capital Structure (M)	Represents the company's financial composition, i.e., the proportion between long-term debt and equity.	$DER = \text{Total Debt} / \text{Total Equity}$ (Brigham & Houston, 2019)	Ratio (Sugiono, 2019)
Firm Value (Y)	Reflects investor expectations regarding the company's future prospects and serves as a primary indicator of performance and investment appeal.	$PBV = \text{Stock Price per Share} / \text{Book Value per Share}$ (Brigham & Houston, 2019)	Ratio (Sugiono, 2019)
Profitability (X1)	Describes the company's ability to generate profit from its assets.	$ROA = \text{Net Income} / \text{Total Assets}$ (Brigham & Houston, 2019)	Ratio (Sugiono, 2019)
Dividend Policy (X2)	Refers to managerial decisions regarding the distribution of earnings to shareholders.	$DPR = \text{Dividend per Share} / \text{Earnings per Share}$ (Brigham & Houston, 2019)	Ratio (Sugiono, 2019)
Size (Control Variable)	The natural logarithm of a company's total assets at the end of the fiscal year serves as a measure of its size and operational capacity.	$\ln(\text{Total Asset})$	Ratio (Sugiono, 2019)
Economic Uncertainty (Control Variable)	Measured through economic uncertainty indices, GDP growth, inflation, and other indicators during the study period, these metrics show the macroeconomic risk levels and dynamics faced by businesses.	1. GDP Volatility; 2. Inflation Rate; 3. Uncertainty Index (World Uncertainty Index – WUI)	Ratio (Sugiono, 2019)

Data Analysis Technique

Data analysis encompassed both descriptive and path analysis methodologies. According to Hayes (2018), the equation for the path analysis model in this study is as follows:

$$\text{Model I: DER} = \alpha + \rho_1\text{ROA} + \rho_2\text{DPR} + \rho_3\text{SIZE} + \rho_4\text{UE} + \varepsilon_1$$

$$\text{Model II: PBV} = \alpha + \rho_5\text{ROA} + \rho_6\text{DPR} + \rho_7\text{DER} + \rho_8\text{SIZE} + \rho_9\text{UE} + \varepsilon_2$$

Where:

M = Capital Structure

Y = Firm Value

α = Constant coefficient

X₁ = Profitability

X₂ = Dividend Policy

Size = Control Variabel

UE = Uncertainty Econoy (Control Variable)

ρ_1 – ρ_8 = Regression coefficients

$\varepsilon_1, \varepsilon_2$ = Residuals

Results and Discussion

Descriptive Analysis

This analysis aims to describe the characteristics of the research data through statistical indicators including average values, highest and lowest observations, as well as the dispersion (standard deviation) for all variables. The following table presents the descriptive statistics for each variable examined.

Table 3. Descriptive Statistics

Statistic	X1 (Profitability)	X2 (Dividend Policy)	M (Capital Structure)	Y (Firm Value)	SIZE	UE (Uncertainty Economy)
Mean	6.524	5.403	1.217	1.311	22.846	110.567
Median	5.330	1.850	0.830	1.000	22.820	110.700
Maximum	32.930	31.450	5.260	4.990	28.010	115.800
Minimum	-0.480	-26.880	0.110	0.190	18.700	105.200
Std. Dev.	5.411	7.612	1.245	1.028	1.859	4.347

A descriptive analysis using company data from 2022-2024 revealed the following statistics: the profitability variable (X1) showed a mean of 6.52 with a standard deviation of 5.41, with some companies experiencing losses (minimum -0.48). The dividend policy variable (X2) had a mean of 5.40 and a standard deviation of 7.61, ranging from -26.88 to 31.45, indicating diverse distribution policies. The average capital structure (M) was 1.22, with a standard deviation of 1.25 (range: 0.11-5.26), suggesting that companies prefer using their own capital. Firm value (Y) had a mean of 1.31 and a standard deviation of 1.03 (range: 0.19-4.99), with most values concentrated in the lower range. The control variables showed stability: company size (SIZE) averaged 22.85 (SD=1.86) and economic uncertainty (UE) averaged 110.57 (SD=4.35). These findings provide insight into the data characteristics for analyzing the relationships between profitability, dividend policy, and firm value, with capital structure as a moderator and size and economic uncertainty as control variables.

Model Selection

The Redundant Fixed Effects Tests (Chow test) within the research model indicate a Cross-section F statistic of 36.67 with a probability of 0.0000, and a Cross-section Chi-square of 349.50, also with a probability of 0.0000. The extremely low probability value (less than 0.05) suggests that the fixed-effect model is more appropriate than the common effect/pooling model. This finding highlights significant variations among individuals in the panel data, necessitating the adoption of the fixed-effect approach to achieve more precise estimation results that accurately capture the unique characteristics of each company.

Table 4. Chow Test (Redundant Fixed Effects Test)

Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	36.666692	(38,74)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	349.495091	38	0.0000

The table above delineates the results of the Chow test, which confirms the statistical significance justifying the selection of the fixed-effects model. Therefore, the panel analysis conducted in this study was appropriately implemented using this approach.

The results of the Hausman test indicate a chi-square statistic of 2.97 with four degrees of freedom, yielding a probability value of 0.5628. Given that this probability exceeds the 0.05 threshold, it implies the absence of a significant difference between the fixed-effect and random-effect models. Therefore, the Random Effect model is considered appropriate for application, as it offers more efficient and unbiased parameter estimates, consistent with the recommendations derived from the Hausman Test results.

Table 5. Hausman Test

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	2.970620	4	0.5628

The selection of the panel analysis model in this study is informed by the Chow test, which indicates the appropriateness of the Fixed Effect model. However, the results of

the Hausman Test suggest that the Random Effect model is also suitable, as there is no evidence of assumption violations within the data. Ultimately, the decision is contingent on the researcher's discretion and the specific characteristics of the data.

The results of the Breusch-Pagan method's Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test reveal a cross-sectional statistical value of 95.44 with a probability of 0.0000. For both hypotheses, the value was 96.95, with a probability of 0.0000. These probability values, which are significantly below the threshold of 0.05, indicate that the random effects model is more appropriate than the common effects (pooled) model. This finding suggests the presence of significant individual effects (cross-section random effects) within the panel data analyzed, thereby recommending the adoption of a random effects model.

Table 6. Breusch-Pagan LM Test

Test	Cross-section	(Prob.)	Time	(Prob.)	Both	(Prob.)
Breusch-Pagan	95.44147	0.0000	1.512255	0.2188	96.95373	0.0000

The table above presents the results of the Breusch-Pagan test for three hypotheses: cross-section, time, and combined (both). The primary conclusion is drawn from the significant values for the cross-section and combined hypotheses, suggesting that the random effects model is appropriate for our data.

Path Analysis

The following analysis examines the results of the structural Model 1, wherein the dependent variable is the capital structure (M), which serves as the intervening variable. This model incorporates profitability (X1), dividend policy (X2), firm size (SIZE), and economic uncertainty (UE) as independent and control variables, employing a random-effects panel EGLS methodology.

Table 7. Structural Model 1

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
Konstanta (C)	-2.763526	1.424376	-1.940166	0.0549
X1 (Profitability)	-0.025314	0.012602	-2.008730	0.0470
X2 (Dividend Policy)	0.000261	0.007037	0.037122	0.9705
SIZE	0.177373	0.055484	3.196826	0.0018
UE	0.000828	0.006823	0.121352	0.9037

The results obtained from the panel data structural model estimation show that profitability exerts a negative and statistically significant influence on capital structure ($p < 0.05$). Conversely, neither dividend policy nor economic uncertainty had a significant impact. Firm size is positively and significantly associated with capital structure, indicating that larger firms tend to utilize more leverage. These findings suggest that, for the companies examined, capital structure decisions are more significantly affected by profitability and firm size than by dividend policies or macroeconomic factors, such as uncertainty. The following table presents the values for R-squared and Adjusted R-squared.

Table 8. Statistic Date of Structural Model 1

Statistic	Value
R-squared (Weighted)	0.094247
Adjusted R-squared (Weighted)	0.061899
F-statistic	2.913515
Prob(F-statistic)	0.024567

In structural model 1, with capital structure as the dependent variable, the R-squared value is 0.094, indicating that the model explains 9.4% of the variation in capital structure, considering factors such as profitability, dividend policy, firm size, and economic uncertainty. The Adjusted R-squared of 0.062 shows minimal improvement from additional independent variables.

Despite low R-squared values, the F-statistic of 2.91 ($p=0.0245$) demonstrates the statistical significance of the overall model, indicating that the variables meaningfully impact capital structure. The model remains suitable for analysis, although future research could explore more relevant variables.

The interpretation of the results for the structural model 2 is as follows: the dependent variable is firm value (Y), with X1 representing profitability, X2 indicating dividend policy, and M serving as the mediating variable for capital structure. Additionally, SIZE and UE (uncertainty economy) were included as control variables, all analyzed using the Panel EGLS Random Effect model.

Table 9. Structural Model 2

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.206163	1.490783	0.138291	0.8903
X1	0.072568	0.013868	5.232935	0.0000
X2	-0.000782	0.008179	-0.095645	0.9240
M	0.158357	0.087625	1.807222	0.0734
SIZE	0.121782	0.054323	2.241813	0.0270
UE	-0.021158	0.008381	-2.524550	0.0130

The results of the panel regression analysis, with firm value as the dependent variable, indicate that both profitability and company size have a positive and statistically significant influence on firm value at the 5% significance level. This finding suggests that the market and investors attribute greater value to firms with substantial profits and larger operational scales.

The analysis further reveals that the role of capital structure as a mediating variable does not significantly affect firm value at the 5% significance level, indicating that its mediating impact is not strongly supported in this model. Similarly, dividend policy does not significantly affect firm value, implying that decisions regarding dividend distribution have not emerged as a critical factor in market valuation during the study period.

Conversely, economic uncertainty negatively and significantly impacts firm value at the 5% significance level. This suggests that unstable economic conditions diminish firm

value, underscoring the importance of managing external risks to preserve corporate values.

In conclusion, this model demonstrates that profitability, company size, and economic stability are the primary determinants of firm values. Capital structure and dividend policy do not been shown to exert significant effects according to the panel data during the study period at a 5% significance level.

The following table and interpretation of R-squared, Adjusted R-squared, and the F test for structural model 2.

Table 10. Statistic Date of Structural Model 2

Statistic	Value
R-squared	0.307404
Adjusted R-squared	0.276206
F-statistic	9.853298
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000

The R-squared value reveals that the model explains approximately 30.7% of the variation in firm value through factors such as profitability, dividend policy, capital structure, firm size, and economic uncertainty. This indicates that while these variables are relatively effective in explaining firm value, approximately 69.3% of the variation is due to factors not included in the model. According to the panel data during the study period, capital structure and dividend policy did not have significant effects at the 5% significance level.

The adjusted R-squared value shows the model's effectiveness after accounting for the number of independent variables included. A value slightly lower than the R-squared suggests that adding independent variables to the model offers a reasonably good contribution, with adjustments for potential bias from irrelevant variables.

The F-statistic test evaluates the model's overall significance. A relatively high F-statistic value and a probability well below 0.05 indicate that the model is significant as a whole, with all variables collectively influencing the firm value.

The following is an interpretation of the mediation test results using SEM PLS bootstrapping 5000.

Table 11. Path Analysis

	Original sample (O)	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Probability -> Capital Structure -> Firm Value	-0.061	-0.061	0.03	2.048	0.041
Dividend Policy -> Capital Structure -> Firm Value	-0.026	-0.026	0.019	1.357	0.175

The pathway through which profitability affects firm value via capital structure is significant, with a p-value of 0.041, which is less than the threshold of 0.05, and the coefficient is negative. This finding indicates that the capital structure plays a crucial role in mediating the impact of profitability on firm value. The negative mediation coefficient suggests that as profitability increases, firm value tends to decrease because of changes in the capital structure. This scenario may occur when more profitable firms choose to reduce their debt levels, thereby decreasing leverage, which inadvertently negatively impacts the company's market value. This could be attributed to market perceptions of the optimal use of external capital.

In the interim, the mediating effect of dividend policy on firm value through capital structure yields a negative coefficient; however, it lacks statistical significance (p-value = 0.175 > 0.05). This indicates that capital structure does not serve as a significant mediator in the relationship between dividend policy and firm value. Essentially, changes in a company's dividend policy do not substantially affect firm value through capital structure alterations.

The Influence of Profitability on Firm Value

This study's findings demonstrate that profitability has a positive and significant impact on the value of service companies in Indonesia from 2022 to 2024. This outcome is consistent with Signaling Theory, which suggests that the market interprets high profitability as a favorable indication of future potential and effective management (Sondakh, 2019). Investors generally perceive companies capable of generating substantial profits as highly competitive, thereby enhancing the firm's perceived value in the public domain.

A considerable body of prior research, including studies by Aprianti et al. (2022); Fuhrotun (2022); Kusumawati et al. (2020); Rachman (2024); Ramadhani et al. (2024); Saputri & Giovanni (2021); Sari & Candra (2024); Wibowo & Yuliana (2020); and Wilson (2020), provides empirical evidence that profitability is a primary determinant of firm value. In Indonesia's service sector, investor confidence in earnings reports has begun to recover post-pandemic, positioning profitability as a critical indicator of business sustainability.

However, it is important to acknowledge that some earlier studies have identified a divergent relationship under specific conditions, such as signal anomalies during periods of heightened uncertainty following the pandemic, (Samiun et al., 2022; Fauziah & Nurhayati, 2023; Mispriyanti & Wicaksono, 2020), when investors became cautious of high profits due to transparency issues or concerns regarding earnings management. This study makes a significant contribution by affirming that the theoretical link between profitability and firm value can dynamically shift based on the characteristics of the era and sector under examination.

The Influence of Dividend Policy on Firm Value

The analysis conducted in this study reveals that dividend policy does not significantly impact the value of service firms in Indonesia during the period under review. The p-

value obtained exceeds the five percent significance threshold, leading to the empirical rejection of the hypothesis that dividends positively influence firm value.

This finding contradicts the Bird-in-the-Hand Theory (Gordon & Lintner) and the Signaling Theory, which propose that investors view dividends as a reliable income source and an indicator of a company's financial stability. Similar discrepancies have been observed in prior research, where factors such as changing investor preferences, concentrated ownership, or the unique characteristics of the service industry suggest that dividends are not always the primary determinant of firm value (Anindya & Muzakir, 2024).

While much of the existing literature (Selvy & Esra, 2022; Seran et al., 2023; Simanjuntak & Hasibuan, 2023; Yanti & Setiawati, 2022) supports the notion that dividends positively influence firm value, this study provides additional contextual evidence that the role of dividends can vary based on industry conditions, market structure, and investor behavior. Consequently, service company management should recognize that a dividend strategy does not invariably enhance firm value and should be integrated with other, more influential factors to shape market perception.

Previous research (Selvy & Esra, 2022; Seran et al., 2023; Simanjuntak & Hasibuan, 2023; Yanti & Setiawati, 2022) has also identified similar trends, underscoring the significance of dividend distribution strategies in enhancing firm value and maintaining shareholder confidence.

However, some studies present differing findings, indicating that in certain contexts, dividend policy may not significantly affect firm value due to more dynamic investor preferences or a concentrated ownership structure (Anindya & Muzakir, 2023; Efpriati & Sumarni, 2024). The findings of this study contribute valuable contextual evidence regarding the role of dividend policy in Indonesian service companies in optimizing market value perception.

The Influence of Profitability on Capital Structure

This study demonstrates that profitability has a negative and significant impact on a company's capital structure. As a company's profitability increases, the proportion of debt in its capital structure decreases, indicating a stronger preference for internal financing. This finding aligns with the Pecking Order Theory, which, although not the primary focus of this study, suggests that companies prioritize internal funding sources, such as retained earnings, before resorting to external financing. Agency Theory also provides insights, indicating that companies with high profitability generally encounter lower agency risks than those with high leverage, which are subject to greater external pressure and oversight from creditors. Empirical evidence from previous studies (Pramana & Darmayanti, 2020; Savitri et al., 2021) supports this mechanism. From a managerial perspective, these results imply that companies should aim to maximize profits before seeking external funds. However, contrasting findings in some earlier studies (Wulandari & Januri, 2020) highlight the need for further investigation, particularly in industries or timeframes with distinct capital structure and profitability characteristics.

Dividend Policy Influences Capital Structure

The findings of this study suggest that dividend policy does not significantly influence the capital structure of service companies in Indonesia. According to Agency Theory, dividends and debt are utilized as mechanisms for managerial oversight to mitigate moral hazards and inefficient fund management. However, in the practical context of Indonesia's service industry, decisions regarding dividend distribution and debt management are frequently made independently, without impacting the capital structure's formation.

These results align with those of several prior studies, such as Mahirun et al. (2023), who identified no significant correlation between dividends and capital structure. Conversely, Mispianiti & Wicaksono (2020; Tayachi et al. (2023); Zou & Bai (2022) identified a positive relationship in companies with varying ownership structures. The discrepancies in these findings can be partially attributed to the differing management perspectives and predominant factors within the companies examined.

Impact of Capital Structure on Firm Value

The research indicates that capital structure does not significantly impact firm value in the service industry. These findings align with the Trade-Off Theory, particularly for service companies that typically do not fully leverage the tax benefits of debt or engage in high-risk debt usage. Instead, firm value is more closely linked to operational performance and profitability than to debt composition.

Supporting these conclusions, previous studies (Ayem & Tamu Ina, 2023; Susanti et al., 2023) have reached similar results, although some studies (Alghifari et al., 2022; Kurniasih et al., 2022) have observed positive outcomes, often in different sectors or among firms with more aggressive leverage strategies.

Capital Structure as a Mediator in the Profitability-Firm Value Relationship

The SEM PLS mediation analysis reveals that capital structure plays a crucial mediating role in the relationship between profitability and firm value, albeit with a negative impact. This finding indicates that firms with higher profitability tend to decrease their debt levels, which subsequently leads to a reduction in their value. This phenomenon may be attributed to the market's perception of optimal leverage or the potential for enhanced investment opportunities when external funding is used. These results align with Agency Theory and corroborate the findings of Mubyarto (2020) and Supeno (2022), who also identified this mediating role, although the direction of the effect may be negative depending on the context. Furthermore, Mercyana et al. (2022), demonstrates that profitability has a notable negative impact on firm value.

Capital Structure as a Mediator in the Impact of Dividend Policy on Firm Value

The results indicate that capital structure does not significantly mediate the relationship between dividend policy and firm value. In service companies, the management of dividend policy and financing is generally conducted independently,

suggesting that the influence of dividend policy on firm value does not occur through capital structure. These findings align with Mispuyanti & Wicaksono (2020), who concluded that capital structure cannot mediate the relationship between dividends and firm value. However, this contrasts with other studies, such as Susanti et al. (2023), which propose that mediation mechanisms may be effective in certain company contexts.

Conclusion

This study investigates the impact of profitability and dividend policy on firm value, with capital structure serving as a mediating variable, specifically in the context of service sector companies in Indonesia. The findings reveal that profitability positively and significantly affects firm value. This outcome supports signaling theory, which suggests that the market views high profitability as indicative of a company's strength and future potential, aligning with most previous research.

In contrast, dividend policy did not have a significant impact on firm value during the study period. This suggests that, within Indonesia's service sector, dividends are not consistently the primary determinant of market value, diverging from the Bird-in-the-Hand Theory and some earlier research findings. Furthermore, profitability negatively and significantly affects capital structure. Firms with high profitability tend to reduce their reliance on debt, consistent with the pecking order and agency theories, which emphasize the importance of internal financing for maintaining governance efficiency and mitigating agency risks.

Additionally, capital structure does not significantly influence firm value, either directly or as a mediator between dividend policy and firm value. However, it negatively mediates the relationship between profitability and firm value. Overall, this study confirms that profitability is the principal determinant of firm value in Indonesia's service sector, while capital structure and dividend policy exert a more limited influence, which is heavily dependent on the specific industry context under investigation.

The limitations of this study primarily pertain to the sample, which is confined to service sector companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange between 2022 and 2024. Consequently, the findings and insights may not be entirely generalizable to other industries or temporal contexts. The variables analyzed are restricted to profitability, dividend policy, capital structure, and firm value, without considering other external factors such as institutional ownership, corporate governance, macroeconomic conditions, and government policies, which could also influence the mechanisms of firm value formation. Additionally, the use of panel data analysis and SEM PLS bootstrapping methods may introduce model bias, particularly in the presence of latent variables or undetected nonlinear relationships.

In light of these limitations, future research should expand the scope to include various industry sectors and extend the observation period to more effectively capture contextual influences and economic fluctuations. Researchers should also consider incorporating additional variables such as institutional ownership, corporate governance, financial report quality, and other pertinent external factors into their analyses. Employing a broader range of methodologies, such as simultaneous structure models or robust testing

with alternative quantitative methods, could enhance the validity of the findings and account for complex inter-variable relationships in future studies. Consequently, future research is expected to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics of firm value formation and the efficacy of managerial strategies in adapting to changes in the business environment.

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